

Managing the Application of Activation of Learners' Accounts of Microsoft O365 (MAALAM) in Taysan National High School

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Abstract:- This study aims to assess the implementation of Managing the Application of Activation of Learners' Accounts Microsoft O365 (MAAAM) in Taysan National High School. The study employed descriptive quantitative research, using a researcher-made questionnaire as a data gathering instrument which 75 class advisers answered. The respondents strongly agree on the goals/objectives with a composite mean of 4.72, 4.80 in terms of learners' account, and 4.77 in teachers' competence. In terms of facilities, the respondents agree with a composite mean of 4.48. Through the use of Facebook messenger and SMS, the distribution of learners' accounts speeds up. There is an increased number of activated accounts through the use of researcher-made flyers and the orientation made by the class advisers and ICT Coordinators. The top five problems that should address in the activation of learners' Microsoft O365 Accounts are lacking mobile devices, financial constraints in buying load, unable to install the application of Microsoft Office, lack of basic ICT knowledge and skills, and the learners are not interested in activating their account. This indicates that the school shall operate the computer laboratories to allow learners to use the functional desktop, laptops, and educational tablets with stable internet connections in an organized manner. The final output is the proposed plan of activities to fully implement the activation of Microsoft O365 and provide Microsoft productivity tools that promote a culture of collaboration and communication and improve the performance of tasks of every learner.

Keywords:- Microsoft O365, Activation, Learner Account.

I. CONTEXT AND RATIONALE

Education is a right of every Filipino. Maximizing the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) improves the quality of education. A nation must produce computer-literate citizens to survive in this digital age. With the delivery of quality instruction, the Digital Literacy skills required under the K-12 curriculum can achieve. To provide quality learning, there is a need access to access 21st century tools that promote the culture of collaboration and communication and improve the performance of tasks.

With the development of the Internet, its expansion, and the access speed increase some tasks can now be done remotely. The idea is that users can use their existing equipment instead of investing in new technology and still get a satisfying service. With his existing equipment, the user accesses the Internet and sends a request for a service which is then replied to.

The Department of Education (DepED) is committed to improving the quality of education by integrating ICT in classroom teaching and upgrading financial management through the automation of key processes. In line with this, DepEd has established the Digital Rise program, a holistic framework that will address the infrastructure, software, and capacity-building requirements in four major components.

The first component is the delivery of the Digital Literacy skills required under the K-12 curriculum. These skills are Productivity Tools in Grades 4 to 6, Basic Programming in Grade 7, Multimedia Skills in Grades 8 to 10, and Vocational Skills in Grades 11 to 12. Microsoft is a key partner in implementing its Digital Rise Program.

Based on the result of the Modified Learner Enrollment and Survey Form (MLESF) in the BOSY 2021, the available device of learners at home that can use in learning are as follows: 2,891 learners have a cellphone, 300 have a cellphone/Desktop/laptop, 53 have a laptop, and 33 have a tablet. 2,122 learners have a way of connecting to the internet through mobile data, broadband, computer shop & other places. 3,389 household members can provide instructional support to the child's distance learning.

The Department of Education continues with its aim of improving governance by providing tools that promote a culture of collaboration and communication and improve the performance of tasks.

According to OUA Memorandum 00-820-0130 or the Guidelines on the Use and Administration of G-Suite and Microsoft 365 for Education, the Department of Education provides employees, teachers, and students with access to twenty-first-century tools that support education and its delivery. This online education package includes tools for email, productivity, and collaboration.

According to OUAD00-0921-0023 or Accelerating DepEd's Computerization Program in view of the COVID - 19 Pandemic, Microsoft Subscription covers a range of products such as Office 365, which is needed to deliver the digital literacy skills component of the K-12 curriculum, Power BI for generating analytics, and Azure Cloud Services where DepEd systems are hosted.

The Department of Education terminated the use of the DepEd workplace and migrated to Microsoft Teams as the new official online communication platform from DepEd Workplace as cited on OUA Memorandum 00-0221-0033.

The study of Simanjuntak, M. et.al (2021) showed that there was an increase in the average score and implied that Microsoft Office 365 is an effective method in teaching writing and is suitable to be applied to those who have high creativity.

The study of Wahyuni, P., & Kusumawati, M. (2021) gleaned that additional internet quota costs are one of the obstacles experienced by the teachers and students in the use of Microsoft Office 365.

The findings of Hasanah, D. R., & Dewi, D. N. (2022) showed that the strategies used by the teachers to solve their problems in teaching online classes are maintaining communication with parents of students, developing thoughtful and creative materials, and making new agreements regarding the online class.

Based on the Beginning of School Year (BOSY) as of November 30, 2021, all learners in Taysan National High School have been issued Microsoft 365 for Education accounts. The Department of Education advised that students must activate their Microsoft 365 for Education accounts and set up a self-service password reset.

The researcher was prompted to conduct a study to help facilitate and speed up the distribution from Grade 7 to Grade 12 learners through Managing the Application of Activation of Learners' Accounts of Microsoft O365 (MAALAM) in Taysan National High School.

A. Action Research Questions

➤ Specifically, it Sought Answers to the Following Questions:

- What is the assessment of Managing the Application of Activation of Learners' Accounts Microsoft O365 in terms of:
 - ✓ Goals/Objectives;
 - ✓ Learners' Account;
 - ✓ Facilities; and
 - ✓ Teachers' Competence?
- What are the possible problems that should be addressed in the activation of learners' Microsoft O365 Accounts?

- Based on the findings, what plan of activities may be proposed for the full implementation of activation of learners' Microsoft O365 Accounts?

II. INNOVATION, INTERVENTION, AND STRATEGY

To facilitate and speed up the distribution of learners' accounts, the researcher assessed the implementation of Project MAALAM: Managing the Application of Activation of Learners' Accounts of Microsoft O365. First,

First, the researcher and the proponents of Project MAALAM conducted an orientation for the adviser last October 27, 2022. The researcher made another succeeding orientation during the 2021 INSET, 2022 Career Expo and School meetings.

Second, the researcher uploaded the excel file to google drive and then shared one link with the adviser. Each adviser classified the name of their learners by encoding the section. After one month, the researcher downloaded the file and then verified in the LIS the name of learners who had not yet been identified. The researcher submitted a letter of request to the District ICT Coordinator to get the Microsoft O365 of Grade 7 learners from their respective Elementary schools. Not all schools submitted learners' accounts. The researcher used the link of admin.microsoft.com to reset the password and give it to the respective adviser of the learner. The researcher consolidated the list of learners per section and uploaded it to google drive, then shared six links to each grade level. The researcher coordinated with the adviser through an official group chat of teachers informing the learners who have not yet been included in their consolidation per section may message the researcher to give their respective accounts. The adviser reported the researcher of the missing learner to provide the Microsoft O365 account with the temporary password. The researcher sent the complete list of learners with MS O365 to the adviser per section.

Third, the researcher developed localized material such as a flyer entitled "*Mga Paraan upang i-activate ang iyong DepEd Microsoft Office 365 account.*" The researcher instructed the advisers and the learners. The researcher distributed self-made developed flyers in the digital and original copies. The researcher provided a contact number to assist via SMS calls and texts and a Facebook messenger account for technical assistance to the learners, parents, and guardians.

A. Action Research Methods

➤ Participants and other Sources of Data Information

No sampling procedure was used in this study since all the 75 advisers from Grade 7 to12 were included as subjects to assess the implementation of Managing the Application of Activation of Learners' Accounts Microsoft O365.

➤ *Research Design*

The study employed the descriptive method of research to assess the implementation of Managing the Application of Activation of Learners’ Accounts Microsoft O365. The researcher used a questionnaire as the main instrument to generate the information needed in the study.

➤ *Data Gathering Methods*

The questionnaire was a tool gathering instrument to collect data. It consisted of two parts; part I pertained to the assessment of Project MAALAM in Taysan National High School concerned with goals/objectives, learners’ accounts, facilities, and teachers’ competence. Part II consisted of items on the possible problems that should address in the activation of learners’ Microsoft O365 Accounts.

The researcher submitted the copy to two ICT Coordinators to validate the questionnaire, enrich the contents and clarify directions. The researcher submitted the questionnaire to an English teacher to improve the structure and for editing purposes.

The researcher asked permission from the principal by a letter of request. Upon approval, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the teacher respondents through the google forms link. After a week, the researcher retrieved the questionnaires. She tallied and tabulated and subjected to statistical treatment for analysis and interpretation.

➤ *Data Analysis Plan*

To answer the problem posed in the study, a weighted mean and ranking were used. After the retrieval of the questionnaires, the data were collated and tabulated. The following scales were utilized in the analysis and interpretation of the data.

Table 1 Data Analysis Plan

Option	Scale/Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.5 - 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.5 – 4.49	Agree
3	2.5 – 3.49	Moderately Agree
2	1.5 – 2.49	Disagree
1	1.0 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree

➤ *Ethical Issues*

The Department of Education (DepED) is committed to improving the quality of education by integrating ICT in classroom teaching, providing tools that promote a culture of collaboration and communication, and enhancing performance tasks. The researcher believes that this study may be significant specifically to students, teachers, parents, school administrators, supervisors, curriculum developers, and future researchers.

All legal procedures were followed in the conduct of this study to ensure that no individual or group may be intimidated or stepped upon. The researcher sought permission from the school head through a formal letter. No part of the paper was copied directly from the works of others to evade plagiarism.

III. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND REFLECTION

The following are the results from the data and the analysis done from the data.

Table 2 Assessment of Objectives of Managing the Application of Activation of Learners’ Accounts Microsoft O365

Objectives	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
The objectives of Managing the Application of Activation of Learners’ Accounts Microsoft O365 ...are specific, measurable, attainable, results-oriented, and time-bound.	4.65	Strongly Agree	5
Ensure the data be kept confidential, and shared only with the concerned account owners, their parents, and/or their section advisers.	4.83	Strongly Agree	1
Speed up the distribution of learners’ Microsoft O365 accounts.	4.66	Strongly Agree	4
Help facilitate activating Microsoft O365 accounts.	4.77	Strongly Agree	2
Use the latest Microsoft productivity tools beneficial in digital education practices.	4.69	Strongly Agree	3
Composite Mean	4.72	Strongly Agree	

As gleaned in Table 2, the objectives of Managing the Application of Activation of Learners’ Accounts Microsoft O365 (MAALAM) ensure learners’ data are kept confidential and strictly adhere to data privacy rules and guidelines. This indicates every learner is given the opportunity to level up and become more equipped to face the challenges of learning ahead of them.

The composite mean of 4.72 interpreted as strongly agree suggests that the implementation of Project MAALAM speed up the distribution of learners’ Microsoft O365 accounts through a well-managed procedure in distribution and activation of their respective account. This is anchored on DepEd OUA 00-0821-0143 which states the need for the activation of learners’ Microsoft O365 accounts. This initiative of the Department of Education that has provided our learners with access to 21st century tools including an online education package supports our school’s thrusts of learning continuity and education delivery. Comprising this package are tools for email, productivity, and collaboration such as Microsoft O365. With these tools afforded to our learners, adapting to the New normal distance learning becomes more readily accessible to them.

The study of Simanjuntak, M. et.al (2021) showed that there was an increase in the average score and implied that Microsoft Office 365 is an effective method in teaching writing and is suitable to be applied to those who have high creativity.

As gleaned in Table 3, it can be noted that the class adviser and the ICT Coordinator of the school shared the DepEd Microsoft Office 365 account with concerned account owners and their parents, or guardians through the use of Facebook messenger chat/calls and SMS calls/texts. The respondents strongly agreed that they distributed the printed copy of the learners' account.

Table 3 Assessment of Learners' Accounts in Managing the Application of Activation of Learners' Accounts Microsoft O365

Learners'	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
The class adviser...			
Used Google Sheets to monitor the complete list of learners' accounts in the respective section.	4.62	Strongly Agree	5
Was assisted by the ICT Coordinator of the school to give the complete list of learners' accounts in the respective section.	4.87	Strongly Agree	2
Used Facebook messenger chat/calls and SMS calls/texts to share the learner's account credentials (username and password) with concerned account owners and their parents, or guardians.	4.92	Strongly Agree	1
Downloaded the file of the learner's account credentials then printed the consolidated copy and cut out the copy of learners' username and password one by one.	4.79	Strongly Agree	3.5
Distributed the printed copy of the learners' username and password to the concerned account owners and their parents or guardians during the distribution and retrieval of modules. beneficial in digital education practices	4.79	Strongly Agree	3.5
Composite Mean	4.80	Strongly Agree	

The composite mean of 4.80 interpreted as strongly agree indicates that every learner has the right to access 21st century tools to deliver quality education. This was supported by OUA Memorandum 00-820-0130 or the Guidelines on the Use and Administration of G-Suite and Microsoft 365 for Education, the Department of Education provides employees, teachers, and students with access to 21st century tools that support education and its delivery. This online education package includes tools for email, productivity, and collaboration.

This affirmed the findings of Hasanah, D. R., & Dewi, D. N. (2022) showed that the strategies used by the teachers to solve their problems in teaching online classes are maintaining communication with parents of students, developing thoughtful and creative materials, and making new agreements regarding the online class.

As gleaned in Table 4, the respondents agreed on implementing Project MAALAM in terms of facilities. The

respondents strongly agree with the provided printed and digital copies of the procedures for activating Microsoft O365. This means that the printed and digital copies contributed to the success of the distribution and activation of learners' accounts. The respondents strongly agreed with the use of DepEd NEAP SIM cards and the survey conducted on the availability of mobile devices with internet connections and mobile data. The respondents agreed on an adequate number of computer units, laptops, and educational tablets, and the school has a functional internet connection.

The respondents agreed on the facilities of Project MAALAM with a composite mean of 4.48. This means that the researcher-made flyers on how to activate Microsoft Office 365 contributed to the distribution and activation of learners' accounts. According to OUAD00-0921-0023, DepEd has replaced existing computer laboratories with mobile laboratories containing tablets and laptops that can move from one classroom to another.

Table 4 Assessment of Facilities of Managing the Application of Activation of Learners' Accounts Microsoft O365

Objectives	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
The school has...			
Functional internet connection.	4.01	Agree	5
Issued DepEd NEAP SIM card with 1 GB mobile data and unlimited all network texts/calls.	4.66	Strongly Agree	2
Provided a printed and digital copy of procedures for activating Microsoft O365.	4.80	Strongly Agree	1
Adequate number of computer units, laptops, and educational tablets.	4.31	Agree	4
Conducted survey on the availability of basic cellphones, smartphones, tablets, and laptops with stable internet connections and mobile data.	4.63	Strongly Agree	3
Composite Mean	4.48	Agree	

This conforms with the study of Simanjuntak, M. et.al (2021) showed that there was an increase in the average score and implied that Microsoft Office 365 is an effective method in teaching writing and is suitable to be applied to those who have high creativity.

As gleaned in Table 4, it is noted that in terms of teachers' competence, the respondents strongly agree with the implementation of Project MAALAM. The class advisers strongly agreed with the training provided by the school ICT Coordinators on the activation of the DepEd Microsoft Office 365 accounts. The respondents strongly agreed on the use of Facebook messenger chat to send the flyers of procedures to Activate DepEd Microsoft Office 365 account. The class advisers assisted learners and their parents or guardians while the ICT Coordinator reset the password of concerned account owners. Lastly, the respondents strongly agreed that they are computer literate.

Table 5 Assessment of Teachers' Competence in Managing the Application of Activation of Learners' Accounts Microsoft O365

Objectives	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
The class advisers...			
Are computer literate	4.72	Strongly Agree	5
Have undergone training on the activation of the DepEd Microsoft Office 365 accounts	4.70	Strongly Agree	1
Seek the help of the ICT coordinator of the school to reset the password of concerned account owners and their parents or guardians	4.85	Strongly Agree	4
Used Facebook messenger chat to send the flyers of procedures to Activate DepEd Microsoft Office 365 account	4.80	Strongly Agree	2
Assisted learners and their parents or guardians to activate the Microsoft O365 account through the use of Facebook messenger chat/calls, SMS calls/texts, and Face-to-Face	4.77	Strongly Agree	3
Composite Mean	4.77	Strongly Agree	

The composite mean of 4.80 interpreted as strongly agree indicates that the class advisers are well-trained in assisting their learners in the activation of the Microsoft O365 accounts. The technical assistance provided by the teachers ensures the success of the implementation of Project MAALAM to achieve better learning outcomes.

This was supported by OUA Memorandum 00-820-0130, users having difficulties accessing their user account may request technical assistance from their assigned User Account Administrator. The findings of Hasanah, D. R., & Dewi, D. N. (2022) showed that the strategies used by the teachers to solve their problems in teaching online classes are maintaining communication with parents of students, developing thoughtful and creative materials, and making new agreements regarding the online class.

Table 6 presents the possible problems that should be addressed in the activation of learners' Microsoft O365 Accounts. It can be gleaned from the table that among the problems, learners' lack of mobile devices (laptop, computer, smartphone, and tablet), rank 1.

This conforms to the findings of Bacolod, D. B. (2022) that mobile internet access through smartphones is the primary educational gadget used by students nowadays. Although there are many existing internet bundles in the country, they are "fluctuating" and are not created equally in terms of speed and stability (Amadora, 2020). Garcia et al. (2020) showed that using the smartphone as an educational tool is very important and that using mobile phones in schools is a proposal that somehow influences the achievement of better academic results. The findings of Demir and Akpinar (2018), suggested that mobile learning may promote students' academic achievement. The students appreciated mobile learning as an approach that may significantly increase their motivation.

Rank 2 is the financial constraints of learners and parents or guardians in buying load to access mobile data. This was supported by the study of Wahyuni, P., & Kusumawati, M. (2021) that additional internet quota costs are one of the obstacles experienced by the teachers and students in the use of Microsoft Office 365.

Table 6 Assessment of Possible Problems in the Implementation of Project MAALAM in Taysan National High School

Possible Problems	Σ of Rank	Rank
1. Lack of administrative support.	60	15
2. Learners' lack of basic ICT knowledge and skills.	160	4
3. Learners' lack of mobile devices (laptop, computer, smartphone, and tablet).	63	1
4. Financial constraints of learners and parents or guardians in buying load to access mobile data.	124	2
5. Unable to send the Microsoft O365 email account and temporary password to concerned account owners and their parents, or guardians.	100	10
6. Lack of communication of learners and their parents or guardians with their respective advisers.	88	8
7. The parent does not allow his/her child to use a smartphone or tablet.	88	8
8. Their sibling does not help the account owner to activate MS O365.	88	8

9. Unable to guide learners, parents, and guardians on provided flyers on how to activate the MS O365 account.	88	11
10. Unable to install Microsoft office due to full storage space of the smartphone and tablet	126	3
11. The learners were not able to communicate on the contact number and a messenger account of the School ICT Coordinator to assist them in activating MS O365.	72	6
12. Unable to provide orientation on the activation of the DepEd Microsoft Office 365 accounts	84	12
13. The School does not form a help desk that will provide assistance to learners, parents, and guardians.	81	13.5
14. The parent or guardian does not allow their child to go to school to guide them in activating the MS O365 account.	81	13.5
15. The learner is not interested in activating their MS O365 account.	165	5

Rank 3 is unable to install Microsoft office due to full storage space of the smartphone and tablet. To get Microsoft Office on Android phone or tablet, there is a need to install the new Office mobile app that combines Word, Excel, and PowerPoint into a single app, and introduces new mobile-centric features to view, edit and share files without the need to switch between multiple apps (Microsoft). Microsoft 365 is a subscription that includes premium versions of Office apps across all your devices, monthly feature updates, and 1 TB of cloud storage. Office 2019 is a one-time purchase that includes classic versions of Office apps installed on one PC or Mac (or 5+ with a volume license).

The findings of the study of Simanjuntak, M. et.al (2021) showed that there was an increase in the average score and implied that Microsoft Office 365 is an effective method in teaching writing and is suitable to be applied to those who have high creativity.

Among the problems assessed by the respondents from rank 4 to 15, there is a need to address the lacking of ICT knowledge and skills that may cause the learner to be not interested in activating their MS O365 account. If the learners were not able to communicate on the contact number and a messenger account of the School ICT Coordinator, there is a need to seek help from the class adviser. Due to lacking communication between learners and their parents or guardians with their respective advisers, the parent does not allow their child to use a smartphone or tablet. In contrast, their sibling does not help the account owner to activate MS O365. As reflected in the table, the distribution of Microsoft O365 email accounts and temporary passwords to concerned account owners through the class advisers and ICT coordinator. Conduct orientation on their parents or guardians using researcher-made flyers on the activation of the DepEd Microsoft Office 365 accounts, provide a helpdesk to assist learners in allowing their parents to go to school, and address the lacking of administrative support.

QUA Memo 00-0821-0143 or Activation of Learners' Microsoft 365, the Office of the Undersecretary for Administration (OUA) released step-by-step materials on activation of learners' Microsoft 365 accounts. In line with this, the researcher made flyers on the step-by-step procedure using the Tagalog version. This conforms with the concepts of multimodal texts, which combine two or more modes such as written language, spoken language, visual (still and moving image), audio, gestural, and spatial

meaning (The New London Group, 2000; Cope and Kalantzis, 2009).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

➤ *From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:*

- The respondents strongly agree in terms of goals/objectives, learners' account and teachers' competence while agree in terms of facilities of Managing the Application of Activation of Learners' Accounts Microsoft O365.
- There were problems that should be addressed in the activation of learners' Microsoft O365 Accounts like lack of mobile devices (laptop, computer, smartphone, and tablet), financial constraints in buying load, full storage space of the smartphone and tablet, lack of basic ICT knowledge and skills, no interest in activating their MS O365 account, unable to communicate the school, lack of communication between class adviser and learners, their parents or guardians, not allowing their child to use a smartphone or tablet, lack of assistance from their sibling to activate MS O365, unable to send the Microsoft O365 email account and temporary password, unable to guide learners, parents, and guardians on provided flyers, unable to provide orientation on the activation of the DepEd Microsoft Office 365 account, no help desk available in the school, not allowing their child to go to school to guide them in activating the MS O365 account and lack of administrative support.
- The final output of the study is the proposed plan of activities for the full implementation of Managing the Application of Activation of Learners' Accounts Microsoft O365.

RECOMMENDATIONS

➤ *From the drawn conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby forwarded.*

- In the distribution of Microsoft O365 and temporary password, the class advisers and ICT coordinators shall ensure learners' accounts are kept confidential, shared only with the owners, their parents or guardians and strictly adhere to data privacy rules and guidelines.

- The school shall provide the digital and printed copies of flyers on the activation of Microsoft O365.
- The school shall form a help desk that will provide technical assistance to students and parents/guardians in activating and resetting of Microsoft O365 account.
- 4.The school shall operate the computer laboratories and allow learners to use the functional desktop, laptops, and educational tablets with stable internet connections.
- The school shall upgrade the internet connectivity and provide a router in a designated building.
- Train class advisers in assisting their learners in the activation of the Microsoft O365 accounts.
- Conduct orientation to learners and parents or guardians on the Microsoft Productivity Tools and activation of Microsoft O365.
- Conduct training among teaching personnel on Microsoft O365, Microsoft Teams, and Other Microsoft Productivity Tools.
- Future researchers may use this manuscript for reference when they conduct studies similar to this current study.

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